
STRATEGY IMPLEMENTATION AND PERFORMANCE OF SELECTED TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN SOUTH-SOUTH NIGERIA

Blessing Ottbong Ette¹

**Department of Business Management, Faculty of Management Sciences
University of Uyo, Nigeria**

Michael Nnameh²

**Department of Business Management, Faculty of Management Sciences
University of Uyo, Nigeria**

Peter Obukor³

**Department of Business Management, Faculty of Management Sciences
University of Uyo, Nigeria**

Ebere Nsikan Udoh⁴

**Department of Business Management, Faculty of Management Sciences
University of Uyo, Nigeria**

Grace Adoga Ugo⁵

**Department of Business Management, Faculty of Management Sciences
University of Uyo, Nigeria**

Abstract

This study was conducted to examine the influence of strategy implementation on the performance selected Tertiary Institutions in South-South Nigeria. The specific objectives were to examine the influence of communication, resource allocation, leadership and commitment on the performance of selected Tertiary Institution in South-South Nigeria. Survey research design was adopted for the study. The population for the study was 15800 respondents and sample size was 390 respondents which were determined using Taro Yamane formula for sample size determination, out of which 366 copies were filled and returned. Data were collected through the use of questionnaire and analyzed using simple linear regression analysis. Findings indicated that communication, resource allocation and leadership and commitment have significant and positive influence on performance of selected tertiary Institution in South-South Nigeria ($P < 0.05$). It was concluded that communication, resource allocation and leadership and commitment jointly influence the performance of selected tertiary Institution in South-South Nigeria. Therefore, it was recommended that tertiary institutions should prioritize the establishment of clear, open, and transparent communication channels between leadership, staff, and student that align with institution's strategic goals and performance expectations and also fostering a positive organizational culture that improving overall performance.

Keywords: Strategy Implementation, Communication, Resource Allocation, Leadership and commitment and Performance

1.1 Introduction

Strategy implementation in tertiary institutions in South Africa is a critical process that involves translating institutional goals into actionable plans aimed at enhancing academic excellence, financial sustainability, and operational efficiency. With higher education facing challenges such as limited funding, changing government policies, student protests, and the need to embrace technological advancements, effective strategy implementation is essential for institutional growth and transformation. Universities and colleges must align their strategic objectives with the needs of the national and global education landscape, fostering a culture of innovation, inclusivity, and accountability. Successful implementation requires strong leadership, adequate resources, and the ability to manage complex external factors such as political and economic shifts, ensuring that institutions meet both academic and social expectations.

The performance of tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria is intricately linked to the effective implementation of strategies, which in turn is influenced by key factors such as communication, leadership and commitment, and resource allocation. Communication plays a critical role in ensuring that strategic goals and objectives are understood, embraced, and executed across all levels of the institution. Effective communication fosters a shared understanding, reduces misunderstandings, and promotes collaboration among faculty, staff, and students, thus facilitating the successful execution of strategies (Okolie & Egbe, 2020). Leadership, particularly at the top levels of management, is another critical factor that determines how well strategies are implemented. Leaders are responsible for setting the direction, motivating stakeholders, and ensuring that resources are utilized effectively. Strong leadership fosters a culture of accountability, innovation, and continuous improvement, all of which are vital for achieving institutional goals (Chukwu & Ugochukwu, 2021). Moreover, leadership commitment is crucial for overcoming resistance to change and rallying support for new initiatives, ensuring the alignment of the institution's objectives with its strategic plans (Ogunyemi & Adebayo, 2021).

Resource allocation is perhaps one of the most pressing challenges facing tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria. Adequate funding and the strategic allocation of resources are essential to the successful implementation of any strategy. Insufficient financial resources and improper allocation of available funds can undermine efforts to improve infrastructure, staff development, and technological adoption, all of which are necessary for enhancing institutional performance (Adedayo & Olalekan, 2022). Many institutions in this region struggle with budget constraints, which hinder their ability to meet the demands of a rapidly changing educational landscape. Moreover, disparities in resource distribution among departments and faculties can lead to unequal development within the institution, further impeding overall performance. Therefore, understanding how communication, leadership, and resource allocation intersect to affect strategy implementation is crucial for improving the performance of tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria.

The performance of universities is increasingly important in shaping the educational landscape and its contribution to national development. Performance in this context refers to the ability of universities to effectively fulfill their core functions, including teaching, research, community engagement, and the employability of graduates (Akanbi and Fadare, 2020). Despite efforts to improve educational standards, universities in the region face significant challenges such as inadequate funding, poor infrastructure, and political instability, which hinder their performance (Olutayo and Olorunfemi, 2020). Furthermore, the

alignment of academic curricula with industry needs remains weak, affecting the employability and skill development of graduates (Nwajiuba and Adetunji, 2020). The limited capacity for strategic planning, evaluation, and performance monitoring also compounds these challenges, preventing universities from achieving their full potential (Olayiwola and Oladipo, 2021). Addressing these barriers is crucial to enhancing the performance of universities in the South-South zone and ensuring that they contribute meaningfully to the socio-economic development of Nigeria.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

In recent years, the implementation of strategies in tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria faces significant challenges due to inadequate communication, which impedes the smooth execution of strategic plans. Effective communication is crucial for aligning stakeholders at all levels—administrators, faculty, and students, toward achieving institutional goals. However, many institutions in the region suffer from poor communication systems, resulting in misunderstandings, confusion, and misalignment between top management and lower-level staff. This breakdown in communication often leads to inefficiencies, delays in decision-making, and a lack of clarity regarding strategic priorities, which ultimately hampers the overall performance of the institution.

Organizational culture also plays a significant role in strategy implementation, and the lack of a supportive culture can negatively impact institutional performance. In many South-South Nigerian tertiary institutions, a culture that is resistant to change, lacking in innovation, or insufficiently collaborative often leads to reluctance in adopting new strategic initiatives. When leadership and employees are not aligned on core values or fail to foster an environment that promotes adaptability and continuous improvement, the execution of strategic plans becomes difficult. This stagnation not only affects the institution's ability to address emerging challenges but also impacts the quality of education and research output, limiting its competitiveness both nationally and internationally.

In addition to communication and culture, resource allocation remains one of the most critical barriers to effective strategy implementation in tertiary institutions. Many universities in South-South Nigeria face resource constraints, including limited financial support, insufficient infrastructure, and inadequate access to modern technology. Without proper resource allocation, the execution of strategic objectives is severely hindered, as institutions struggle to maintain basic operational needs, let alone invest in new initiatives. Furthermore, leadership and commitment are essential for navigating these challenges. Weak leadership or lack of commitment from top management can exacerbate these issues, resulting in ineffective resource utilization, poor planning, and a failure to secure necessary funding. Ultimately, these combined challenges of communication, organizational culture, resource allocation, and leadership directly undermine the performance of tertiary institutions in the region, limiting their ability to fulfill their educational mission and remain competitive on both a national and global scale. Yes, studies have conducted on strategy implementation and performance but most of this study focused on business organizations especial SMEs with a little interest on Tertiary institutions.

Therefore, this study was carried to examine the influence of strategy implementation and the performance of selected Tertiary Institutions in South-South Nigeria.

The main objective of the study was to examine the influence of strategic implementation on the performance of Universities in South-south, Geo-Political Zone, Nigeria. Specifically, to:

- i. examine the influence of communication on performance of Universities in South-South Geo-Political zone, Nigeria.
- ii. examine the influence of resource allocation on performance Universities in South-South Geo-Political Zone, Nigeria.
- iii. investigate the influence of leadership and commitment on performance Universities in South-South Geo-Political Zone, Nigeria.

The following research questions were asked to guide the study:

- i. What is the influence of communication on performance Universities in South-South Geo-Political Zone, Nigeria?
- ii. How does resource allocation influence the performance Universities in South-South Geo-Political Zone, Nigeria?
- iii. What influence has leadership and commitment on the performance of Universities in South-South Geo-Political Zone, Nigeria?

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

H₀₁: There is no significant influence of communication on performance of selected Tertiary Institutions in South-South Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant influence of resource allocation on performance selected Tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria.

H₀₃: There is no significant influence of leadership and commitment on the performance selected Tertiary institution in South-South, Nigeria.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.2 Strategy Implementation

Effective strategy implementation is a critical factor influencing organizational performance, particularly in educational institutions. A study by Omotayo and Olayinka (2021) highlights that strategic management practices, including clear goal-setting, resource alignment, and performance monitoring, are fundamental to improving institutional outcomes. The researchers argue that when higher education institutions implement well-defined strategies, they are better positioned to adapt to changing educational demands, enhance teaching quality, and improve overall operational efficiency. Moreover, the involvement of leadership in fostering a culture of strategic awareness and commitment significantly boosts performance outcomes, as strategic alignment at all levels of the institution leads to more cohesive efforts in achieving institutional goals (Omotayo and Olayinka, 2021).

Furthermore, recent studies show that the successful implementation of strategies is also closely linked to organizational culture and the adaptability of staff. According to Ajayi *et al.* (2022), organizational culture, particularly in the context of shared values and norms, plays a pivotal role in how strategies are executed and how effectively they contribute to

performance improvements. In their research, they observe that institutions with a culture that promotes innovation and collaboration tend to perform better in terms of both academic and administrative outcomes. The integration of technology and the fostering of a learning-oriented environment are other key components that enhance the effectiveness of strategic initiatives. These findings demonstrate that successful strategy implementation not only relies on the technical aspects of planning and resource allocation but also on cultivating a culture that supports continuous improvement and adaptation to new challenges (Ajayi *et al.*, 2022).

Conceptual Specification of Model

Figure 1: Conceptual Model showing the interaction between the independent variables and the dependent variable

Source: Researcher's Conceptualization (2025)

2.1.3 Communication

Effective communication significantly influences the performance of tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State, particularly concerning strategy implementation. A study comparing employee communication practices and communication climates between Akwa Ibom State Polytechnic, Ikot Osurua, and Heritage Polytechnic, Eket, found that both institutions prioritize free information flow, adherence to rules, and promotion of innovation. These practices foster a positive communication climate, which is essential for implementing institutional strategies effectively.

Additionally, research on digital media usage for information dissemination in Akwa Ibom's tertiary institutions reveals that electronic communication methods, such as voice-mail and picture messages, significantly enhance organizational communication. The study indicates that the effective use of these digital tools facilitates timely and efficient information flow, thereby supporting the successful implementation of institutional strategies.

2.1.4 Resource Allocation

Resource allocation plays a critical role in the performance of tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, especially concerning strategy implementation. A 2024 study by Nwosu *et al.* examined the impact of educational financing and funds management on the

effectiveness of post-secondary schools in the state. The research revealed that inadequate funding and poor funds management practices significantly hinder the effectiveness of these institutions. The study concluded that involving the public in evaluating school expenditures and promoting transparency could enhance resource utilization and, consequently, institutional performance.

Furthermore, research on strategic management practices within Akwa Ibom's civil service highlights the importance of resource allocation in strategy implementation. The study found that strategic planning and strategic choices positively and significantly influence organizational performance. It recommended improving the strategic planning process through adequate resource allocation to enhance organizational performance.

2.1.5 Leadership and Commitment

Leadership commitment significantly influences the performance of tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State, particularly concerning strategy implementation. A study by Izuka and Ukpai (2024) investigated the relationship between performance management and employee commitment in these institutions. The findings revealed that performance management, when moderated by a positive organizational climate, positively impacts employee commitment. This commitment, in turn, enhances institutional performance, underscoring the importance of leadership in fostering such an environment.

Moreover, transformational leadership has been identified as a key factor in achieving organizational success within tertiary institutions. Research by Okoli et al. (2021) demonstrated a strong positive correlation between transformational leadership dimensions—such as idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration—and organizational success. This study highlights that leadership commitment to transformational practices can lead to significant improvements in institutional performance, particularly during strategy implementation phases.

2.1.6 Performance

Any business organization must prioritize performance. This is so because generating profits is the main goal of a business. The performance of a business demonstrates its ability to meet objectives by efficiently utilizing its resources (Edward, 2016). Three distinct categories make up an organization's performance. These aspects include financial performance, which includes things like profits, return on investment, and asset returns, among other things; performance may also be related to products. Performance indicators for the product market, such as sales and market share, may be included. Once more, performance can be evaluated in terms of shareholder return, including total shareholder return and economic value contributed (Richard, 2019).

2.2 Theoretical Review

The Resource-Based Theory

The Resource-Based View (RBV) theory, developed by Birger Wernerfelt in 1984 and later expanded by scholars like Barney (1991) and Prahalad and Hamel (1990), posits that a firm's internal resources and capabilities are the primary drivers of competitive advantage and superior performance. According to RBV, resources must be valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable (VRIN) to provide sustained competitive advantage (Barney, 1991). This theory shifts the focus from external market conditions to the internal strengths of the

organization, highlighting the importance of leveraging unique resources, including human capital, technology, and organizational culture, to achieve success. In the context of tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria, these internal resources can significantly impact the quality of education, research output, and institutional reputation.

The implementation of strategic initiatives in tertiary institutions relies heavily on the effective utilization of these internal resources to enhance performance. For instance, the availability of skilled academic staff, state-of-the-art facilities, and access to research funding are crucial resources that can drive strategic goals such as improving academic performance and increasing research output (Ike and Uzochukwu, 2021). By applying the RBV framework, universities in South-South Nigeria can develop unique capabilities that differentiate them from others, positioning themselves for better resource allocation, student enrollment, and external collaborations. Furthermore, leveraging these resources can lead to improved institutional performance and the ability to meet the increasing demand for quality education.

In practice, the RBV theory suggests that strategic management in Nigerian tertiary institutions should focus on developing and nurturing these resources to ensure sustainable success. The growing challenges of underfunding, infrastructure decay, and limited access to advanced technologies in the region highlight the need for strategic resource management (Okafor and Ifeanyi, 2020). By aligning their strategies with the RBV, institutions can not only improve their operational efficiency but also enhance their long-term viability and reputation on both local and international platforms. Ultimately, the RBV provides a valuable framework for tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria to optimize their internal resources, improve strategic implementation, and foster better performance outcomes.

2.3 Empirical Review

Chima *et al.* (2023) examined performance management and employees' Commitment in Tertiary Institutions in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The objective was to investigate the relationship between performance management and employee commitment, moderated by organizational climate, in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State. The research design adopted Survey design. The population for the study was 2,725 academic staff from seven tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State with sample size of 349 respondents. Data were collected using Administration of validated questionnaires performance management questionnaire (PMQ) and Employees' Commitment Questionnaire (ECQ) with reliability coefficients of 0.87 and 0.79, respectively and were analysed using frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation, and moderator regression analysis at a 0.05 significance level. Findings indicated that performance management practices alone do not significantly enhance employee commitment. However, the presence of a positive organizational climate strengthens this relationship. It was concluded that integrating performance management with a supportive organizational climate is essential for boosting employee commitment in tertiary institutions. It was recommended that collaborative development of performance objectives between administrators and employees to enhance understanding and reduce conflicts.

Victor and Ita (2017) examined effects of communication and participative decision making on employees' commitment in Akwa Ibom State Civil Service. The objective was to assess how communication and participative decision-making influence employee commitment within Akwa Ibom State's civil service. The research design adopted was survey research method. The population of the study was civil servants across ten ministries and extra-ministerial departments in Akwa Ibom State with sample size of 400 respondents. Data were

collected using structured questionnaire and analysed using analysis of responses to evaluate the impact of communication and participation on employee commitment. Findings revealed that active employee involvement in decision-making and effective communication systems significantly enhance job commitment. It was recommended promoting participative decision-making and open communication fosters higher employee commitment in the civil service. It was recommended that establishment of collaborative efforts among stakeholders to improve communication and involve employees in decision-making processes.

Daniel Akarika (2023) examined an appraisal of organizational communication and job Satisfaction among academic staff in Akwa Ibom State University. The objective was to examine the impact of organizational communication on job satisfaction among academic staff at Akwa Ibom State University. Survey research design was adopted for the study. The population was academic staff of Akwa Ibom State University with the sample size of 44 respondents. Data were collected using questionnaire and analysed using correlation analysis and analysis of responses to assess the influence of communication on job satisfaction. Findings indicated effective organizational communication positively influences job satisfaction among academic staff. It was concluded that enhancing communication within the university can lead to higher job satisfaction among faculty members. It was recommended that improvement of communication policies and structures to boost job satisfaction.

Onyekwelu (2020) investigated the effects of strategic management on organizational performance in manufacturing firms in South-East Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population of the study was made up of 1200 selected manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria. The major instrument used in the study was the questionnaire. Multiple regression analysis was employed in analyzing the data using a 5% level of significance. Strategic management showed significant effect on organizational performance of manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria. It was concluded that strategic management can determine organizational performance of manufacturing firms in the South Esat zone of Nigeria. It was recommended that manufacturing firms sustain the application of strategic management in their operations given turbulent and hyper competitive environment in which such firms operated.

Olanipekun *et al.* (2015) examined the impact of strategic management on competitive advantage and organization performance in Nigerian Bottling Company. The study used primary data with the aid of a structured questionnaire which was used to elicit information from respondents. The data collected were analyzed using both descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages mean, standard deviation and inferential statistical tool of Chi-square. The findings revealed that indeed the adoption and implementation of strategic management practices makes the organization not only to be proactive to changes but also initiate positive changes that consequently leads to competitive advantage and sustainable performance. The reviewed study was on impact of strategic management on competitive advantage and organization performance and it was a case study compared to the present study which is on strategic management and SMEs performance. Also, while the reviewed study used Chi-square in data analysis, the present study uses regression method of data analysis.

2.3.1 Gap in Knowledge

Despite extensive research on strategy formulation, implementation, evaluation, and control in various sectors, there remains a notable gap in literature regarding their specific influence on the performance of universities, particularly in developing countries like Nigeria. While scholars have explored the impact of strategic management on organizational performance, the unique context of universities such as the complex nature of their goals (educational, research, social service), bureaucratic structures, and resource limitations has not been sufficiently addressed. Most studies focus on the private sector or large corporations, leaving the educational sector under-explored. Additionally, while strategy formulation and implementation are often discussed in isolation, there is limited research on how these processes interact with strategy evaluation and control mechanisms to influence the overall performance of universities. The existing literature also tends to overlook how contextual factors such as local political dynamics, cultural differences, and resource constraints affect the execution and outcomes of these strategies in universities, particularly in the South-South region of Nigeria. This gap highlights the need for more focused research to understand the full cycle of strategic management in universities and its direct impact on institutional performance.

3.1 Methodology

The survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consisted of 15800 staff made up of the three Federal universities selected for the study. Sample size for the study was 390 respondents which were determined using Taro Yamen's formula of 1967 for sample size determination. And the proportional distribution was used to allocate the sample size since the population was not obtained from a particular University selected for the study. Data were collected using questionnaire and was designed using modified four-point rating scale, ranging from Strongly agree(SA-4), Agree (A-3), Disagree (D-2), Strongly Disagree (SD-1) and . Two senior lecturers in Business Management were consulted to assist in examining and advising on the face and content validation of the instrument. The instrument had a Cronbach Alpha coefficient of 0.77. However, since the population of the study was collected from a particular university, therefore the proportional allocation formula was used to distribute the sample size across the three federal universities selected for the study based on their years of operation. It also recorded a response rate of 76.47. Data were analyzed using percentage and simple linear regression analysis. The simple percentage was used to analyse the research questions while simple linear regression was used to test the null hypotheses formulated for the study.

3.2 Model Specification

The model indicates functional and linear equation of the interaction between strategy implementation dimensions and performance of the selected Tertiary institutions in south-south Nigeria. It further revealed that communication, resource allocation, leadership and commitment are the functions of performance in Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria. This was estimated using mathematical models:

$P = f(C)$	Model	3.1
$P = a_0 + a_1C + e$	Equation	3.1
$P = f(RA)$	Model	3.2
$P = a_0 + a_1RA + e$	Equation	3.2
$P = f(LC)$	Model	3.3

$$P = a_0 + b_1 LC + e$$

Equation 3.3

Where;

a = Interception of the equation

P= Performance

C = Communication

RA=Resource Allocation

LC=Leadership and Commitment

a₁ a₂= Coefficients of the Independent variables

e = Error term

Data Presentation and Analysis Questionnaire Administered and Retrieved

Table 4.1: Distribution of Questionnaire

	Questionnaire Administered	Questionnaire Returned	Percentage Returned
University of Benin	197	190	94.3%
University of Calabar	148	141	
University of Port Harcourt	45	35	
Total	390	366	94.3%

Source: Researcher's Compilation, 2025

Table 4.1 Indicates that 197 copies of questionnaire were distributed to university of Benin but 190 copies of the questionnaire were filled and returned while 148 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to University of Calabar but 141 were correctly answered and returned. Also, 45 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the University of Port Harcourt but 35 were filled and returned and it shows 94.3% response rate

Descriptive Analysis

Research Questions

Research question 1

What is the influence of communication on performance of selected Tertiary Institution in South-South Nigeria?

Table: 4.2. Responses on communication and performance of Selected tertiary Institution in South-South Nigeria

Questionnaire	SA	A	D	SD	Total
Information within the institution is regularly shared through clear and effective channels	134 (36.6%)	160 (43.7%)	39 (10.7%)	33 (9.0%)	366 (100%)
Information from management to staff is transparent and timely.	131 (35.8%)	161 (44.0%)	40 (10.9%)	35 (9.6%)	366 (100%)
The system in the institution facilitates the smooth implementation of strategies.	135 (36.9%)	163 (44.5%)	41 (11.2%)	27 (7.4%)	366 (100%)
There is effective feedback staff and students to management regarding institutional performance	136 (37.2%)	159 (43.4%)	39 (10.7%)	32 (8.7%)	366 (100%)
Mean	134	161	40	32	366

Source: Researcher’s Computation, 2025

Table 4.2 indicates that 134 respondents representing 36.6% strongly agree that Information within the institution is regularly shared through clear and effective channels, while 160 respondents representing 43.7% agree, but 39 respondents representing 10.7% disagree and 33 respondents representing 9.0 % strongly disagree that Information within the institution is regularly shared through clear and effective channels. Also, 131 respondents representing 35.8% strongly agree that information from management to staff is transparent and timely. While 163 respondents representing 43.7 %agree but 40 respondents representing 10.9 % disagree and 35 respondents representing 9.6% strongly disagree that Information from management to staff is transparent and timely. Furthermore, 135 respondents representing 36.9% strongly agree .The system in the institution facilitates the smooth implementation of strategies while 163 respondents representing 44.5% agree but 41 respondents representing 11.2 % disagree and 27 respondents representing 7.4% strongly disagree that the system in the institution facilitates the smooth implementation of strategies. In addition, 136 respondents representing 37.2 % strongly agree that there is effective feedback staff and students to management regarding institutional performance while 159 respondents representing 43.4% agree, but 39 respondents representing 10.7% disagree and 32 respondents representing 8.7% strongly disagree that there is effective feedback staff and students to management regarding institutional performance

Research question 2

What is the influence of strategy implementation on performance of selected Tertiary Institutions in South-South Nigeria?

Table: 4.3: Responses on resource allocation and Performance of Tertiary Institutions in South-South Nigeria

Questionnaire	SA	A	D	SD	Total
The institution releases sufficient financial resource to support its strategic objective	147 (40.2%)	175 (47.8%)	24 (6.6%)	20 (5.5%)	366 (100%)
Human resources are adequately supported with training and development opportunities	170 (46.4%)	152 (41.5%)	25 (6.8%)	19 (5.2%)	366 (100%)
I allocate resources to enhance implementation of plans and improvement in institution performance	172 (47.0%)	150 (41.0%)	20 (5.5%)	24 (6.6%)	366 (100%)
Strategic goals and objectives are aligned in my institution to improve performance	171 (46.7%)	151 (41.3%)	26 (7.1%)	18 (4.9%)	366 (100%)
Mean	165	157	24	20	312

Source: Researchers' Computation, 2025

Table 4.3 shows that 147 respondents representing 40.2% strongly agree that the institution releases sufficient financial resource to support its strategic objective while 175 respondents representing 47.8% agree but 24 respondents representing 6.6% disagree and 20 respondents representing 5.5 % strongly disagree that the institution releases sufficient financial resource to support its strategic objective. Also, 170 respondents representing 47.0% strongly agree that human resources are adequately supported with training and development opportunities while 152 respondents representing 41.5% agree but 25 respondents representing 6.8% and 19 respondent representing 5.2% strongly disagree that human resources are adequately supported with training and development opportunities. In the same vein, 172 respondents representing 47.0% strongly that they allocate resources to enhance implementation of plans and improvement in institution performance while 150 respondents representing 41.0 agree but 20 respondents representing 5.5% disagree and 24 respondents representing 6.6% strongly disagree that they allocate resources to enhance implementation of plans and improvement in institution performance. Furthermore, 171 respondents representing 46.7 % strongly agree that Strategic goals and objectives are aligned in my institution to improve performance while 151 respondents representing 41.3% but 26 respondents representing 7.1% disagree and 18 respondents representing 4.9% strongly disagree that Strategic goals and objectives are aligned in my institution to improve performance.

Research question 3

What influence has leadership and commitment on the performance of selected Tertiary Institutions in South-South Nigeria?

Table: 4.4: Responses on Leadership and Commitment and Performance of Selected Tertiary Institutions in South-South Nigeria.

Questionnaire	SA	A	D	SD	Total
The institution demonstrate a strong commitment to achieving institution goals	145 (39.6%)	170 (46.4%)	22 (6.0%)	29 (7.9%)	366 (100%)
Strategic planning and decision-making process in my institution are actively implemented to enhance performance.	147 (40.7%)	169 (46.1%)	20 (5.5%)	30 (8.2%)	366 (100%)
My institution supports innovation and improvement that help to implement strategy and enhance performance	149 (40.7%)	167 (45.6%)	31 (8.5%)	19 (5.2%)	366 (100%)
My unit head provides sufficient motivation and incentives to staff to achieve institutional goals	151 (41.3%)	160 (43.7%)	43 (11.7%)	12 (3.3%)	366 (100%)
Mean	148	167	29	23	366

Source: Researcher's Computation, 2025

Table 4.4 shows that 145 respondents representing 39.6% strongly agree that The institution demonstrate a strong commitment to achieving institution goals while 170 respondents representing 46.4% agree but 22 respondent representing 6.0% disagree and 29 respondents representing 7.9% strongly disagree that The institution demonstrate a strong commitment to achieving institution goals. Also, 147 respondents representing 40.7% strongly agree that strategic planning and decision-making process in my institution are actively implemented to enhance performance, but 20 respondents representing 5.5 disagree and 30 respondents representing 5.2% strongly disagree that strategic planning and decision-making process in my institution are actively implemented to enhance performance. Similarly, 149 respondents representing 40.7% strongly agree that their institution supports innovation and improvement that help to implement strategy and enhance performance while 167 respondents representing 45.6% agree but 31 respondents representing 8.5% disagree and 19 respondents representing 5.2 strongly disagree that their institution supports innovation and improvement that help to implement strategy and enhance performance. Also, 151 respondents representing 41.3 strongly agree that their unit head provides sufficient motivation and incentives to staff to achieve institutional goals while 160 respondents representing 43.7% agree but 43 respondents representing 11.7% disagree and 12 respondents representing 3.3% strongly disagree that their unit head provides sufficient motivation and incentives to staff to achieve institutional goals,

Test of Hypotheses

Test of hypothesis One

Hypothesis 1

H₀₁: There is no significant influence of communication on performance of SMEs in Akwa Ibom State

H₁₁: There is a significant influence of communication on performance of SMEs in Akwa Ibom State

Table 4.5 : The Simple Linear Regression Analysis on the influence of communication on Performance of Selected Tertiary Institution in South-South Nigeria

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.886 ^a	.784	.784		.47008	1.398

Model Fit

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	292.680	1	292.680	1324.495	.000 ^b
	Residual	80.435	364	.221		
	Total	373.115	365			

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.289	.052		5.563	.000
	Communication	.829	.023	.886	36.394	.000

Source: Researcher's Computation , 2025

Table 4.5 indicates the simple linear regression analysis on the influence of communication on performance of selected Tertiary institutions in south-south Nigeria. The result yields the R^2 value of .782, Durbin Watson coefficients of 1.398, F- value of 1324.495, P-value of .000 and Beta coefficients of .829. This implies that communication can account for 78.4 % change in performance of selected tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria. The result is supported by Beta coefficients of .829 which means that 1 unit increase of communication would lead to .829 increases in performance of selected Tertiary institutions in south- south .Also, to evaluate the presence of auto-correlation in the model, the Durbin Watson statistics were computed and results yield the coefficients of 1.398 suggesting that there is absent of auto-correlation in the model. The F-statistics were further computed to measure the fit of the model and result yield 1324.495 goodness of fit implying that the model is fit to evaluate the interaction between communication and performance of selected Tertiary Institution in south-South Nigeria. Therefore, since the F- value of 1324.495 and the P-value .000 lies below the Alpha value of 0.05 level of significant in social sciences, It can be concluded that communication has significant and positive influence on performance of selected Tertiary institutions in south-south Nigeria, meaning that the Null hypothesis which states that there is no significant influence of communication on performance of selected Tertiary institutions in south-south Nigeria is rejected and alternative accepted

Hypothesis 2

H₀₁: There is no significant influence of resource allocation on performance of SMEs in Akwa Ibom State

H_{i1}: There is a significant influence of resource allocation on performance of SMEs in Akwa Ibom State

Table 4.6: The Simple Linear Regression Analysis on the Influence of resource allocation on Performance of Selected Tertiary Institution in South-South Nigeria

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.854 ^a	.729	.728	.52725	1.008

Model Fit

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	271.927	1	271.927	978.190	.000 ^b
	Residual	101.188	364	.278		
	Total	373.115	365			

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.174	.063		2.758	.006
	resource allocation	.800	.026	.854	31.276	.000

Source: Researcher's Computation ,2025

Table 4.6 shows the simple linear regression analysis on the influence of resource allocation on performance of selected Tertiary institutions in south-south Nigeria. The result yields the R^2 value of .729, Durbin Watson coefficients of 1.008, F- value of 978.190, P-value of .000 and beta coefficients of .800. This implies that resource allocation can account for 72.9% change in performance of selected tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria. The result is supported by beta coefficients of .800 which means that 1 unit increase of resource allocation would lead to .829 increases in performance of selected tertiary institutions in south- south. Also, to evaluate the presence of auto-correlation in the model, the Durbin Watson statistics were computed and results yield the coefficients of 1.008 suggesting that there is absent of auto-correlation in the model. The F-statistics were further computed to measure the fit of the model and result yield 978.190 goodness of fit implying that the model is fit to evaluate the interaction between resource allocation and performance of selected tertiary institution in south-south Nigeria. Therefore, since the F- value of 978.190 and the P-value .000 lies below the alpha value of 0.05 level of significant in social sciences, It can be concluded that resource allocation has significant and positive influence on performance of selected Tertiary institutions in south-south Nigeria, meaning that the Null hypothesis which states that there is no significant influence of resource allocation on performance of of selected Tertiary institutions in south-south Nigeria is rejected and alternative accepted

Hypothesis 3

H₀₁: There is no significant influence of leadership and commitment on performance of SMEs in Akwa Ibom State

H_{i1}: There is a significant influence of strategy evaluation and control on performance of SMEs in Akwa Ibom State

Table 4.7 : The Simple Linear Regression Analysis on the Influence of leadership and commitment on Performance of Selected Tertiary Institution in South-South Nigeria

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.909 ^a	.827	.826	.42125	.970

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	308.521	1	308.521	1738.590	.000 ^b
	Residual	64.594	364	.177		
	Total	373.115	365			

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.294	.045		6.460	.000
	leadership and commitment	.745	.018	.909	41.696	.000

Source: Researcher's Computation, 2025

Table 4.7 shows the simple linear regression analysis on the influence of leadership and commitment on performance of selected tertiary institutions in south-south Nigeria. The result yields the R^2 - value of .827, F- value of .1738.590, P-value of .000 and Beta coefficients of 745. This implies that resource allocation can account for 82.7% change in performance of selected tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria. The result is supported by Beta coefficients of .745 which means that 1 unit increase of leadership and commitment would lead to .829 increases in performance of selected tertiary institutions in south- south .Also, to measure the goodness of fit of the model, the F-statistics was further computed and result yield 1738.590 goodness of fit implying that the model is fit to evaluate the interaction between leadership and commitment and performance of selected tertiary institution in south-South Nigeria. Therefore, since the F- value of 1738.590 and the P-value of .000 lies below the Alpha value of 0.05 level of significant in social sciences, It can be concluded that leadership and commitment has significant and positive influence on performance of selected tertiary institutions in south-south Nigeria, meaning that the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant influence of leadership and commitment on performance of selected tertiary institutions in south-south Nigeria is rejected and alternative accepted

4.3 Discussion of Findings

There is significant influence of communication on the Performance of selected Tertiary Institutions in South-South Nigeria

The finding in hypothesis one indicated that there is significant influence of communication on the performance of selected Tertiary institutions in south-south Nigeria. This finding is

supported by the work of Oduro and Agyekum (2022) who highlighted that higher education institutions with well-defined strategic goals, aligned with both internal capabilities and external market trends, perform better in terms of academic output, research productivity, and global rankings. In particular, institutions that integrate innovative teaching, research agendas, and community engagement into their strategic plans tend to improve their global standing and local impact. The findings are further supported by the works of Oduro and Agyekum (2022) and Harrison and Carroll (2020) who reveal that strategic alignment with societal needs, such as meeting labor market demands, is key. A study by Brown and Jones (2020) suggests that institutions that communicate its strategy stands a better chance to adapt to future challenges and provide relevant education to students, thereby enhancing institutional reputation and student satisfaction. Also, the findings on the influence of communication on performance in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State underscore the importance of these factors in enhancing institutional outcomes. Research has shown that effective communication plays a pivotal role in fostering employee engagement and commitment, which ultimately translates into improved organizational performance. This is supported by the work of Ekanem *et al.* (2019) who revealed that transparent and open communication channels lead to higher levels of staff motivation and commitment, which enhances their overall performance. Furthermore, leadership and commitment emerged as crucial factors influencing the success of these institutions. The leadership style within an institution shapes its strategic direction and the commitment levels of its staff. A transformational leadership approach, where leaders inspire and motivate their teams through vision and shared goals, has been linked to improved institutional performance.

This finding aligns with the work of Udo *et al.* (2018), who emphasized the role of leadership in fostering a performance-oriented culture in Nigerian universities. Additionally, when leadership supports and commits to the institutional goals, it cultivates a culture of performance and commitment among staff, as seen in the study of tertiary institutions. The finding is in agreement the work of Effiong and Bassey (2021) who highlight the synergy between leadership, resource allocation, communication, and commitment as key drivers of strategy implementations and performance in educational institutions.

There is significant influence of resource allocation on the Performance of selected Tertiary Institutions in South-South Nigeria

There is significant influence of leadership and commitment on the Performance of selected Tertiary Institutions in South-South Nigeria. This finding is agreement the work of González and Martínez, (2021) and Lee and Park (2022) who stated that the use of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and regular performance reviews helps identify areas requiring improvement, fostering a culture of accountability and continuous improvement. Additionally, these evaluations provide critical insights that inform future strategic formulations and implementation efforts, creating a feedback loop that improves the overall effectiveness of the institution. Also, the finding is supported by the work of Hossain and Ghosh (2021) who indicated that tertiary institutions that adapt their strategies in response to changes in external factors tend to outperform those that fail to do so. For instance, institutions that embraced digital learning technologies during the COVID-19 pandemic experienced less disruption and better maintained their performance levels. . Similarly, resource allocation, particularly the provision of adequate funding for infrastructural development and academic resources, was found to positively affect institutional performance. This is consistent with findings from Okorafor and Opara (2020), who found that universities with better resource allocation strategies perform better in academic

achievements and student satisfaction. Therefore, the ability of these institutions to allocate resources efficiently and communicate effectively determines their capacity to deliver on their educational mandate. The finding is in agreement the work of Okon et al. (2022) who found out that there is a significant positive effect of staff mix utilization on productivity, highlighting that aligning staff qualifications and experience with institutional needs enhances performance. Conversely, factors like work-life balance, motivation, and incentives negatively affected efficiency and service delivery, suggesting that resource allocation should also consider employee welfare to optimize performance.

There is significant influence of leadership and commitment on the Performance of selected Tertiary Institutions in South-South Nigeria

The finding of hypothesis two showed that there is significant influence of strategy formulation on the Performance of selected Tertiary Institutions in South-South Nigeria. This finding is in agreement the work of Nkansah and Yeboah (2021) who opined that effective implementation can lead to higher levels of institutional performance, including improved student retention rates, graduation rates, and employability of graduates. This is supported by the work of Al-Nashash (2020) who found that strong leadership, a clear communication strategy, and robust resource allocation systems are essential for successful implementation in higher education institutions. Institutions with a participative leadership style that involves faculty, staff, and students in the decision-making process are more likely to overcome barriers and achieve their strategic objectives. The finding also is in line with the work of Zohreh and Soltani (2023) who revealed that universities that align their teaching and research processes with their strategic plan show significant improvements in both academic quality and stakeholder satisfaction. The alignment also facilitates better financial management, improved academic staff performance, and stronger institutional governance. Resource allocation significantly influences the performance of tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State, impacting areas such as infrastructure development, instructional quality, and overall institutional effectiveness. This is supported by the work of Nwosu et al. (2024) who revealed that inadequate funding and ineffective fund management practices hinder the effectiveness of post-secondary schools in the state. The research indicated that the nature of funding is insufficient, and the management of available funds by institutional heads is ineffective, leading to suboptimal educational outcomes. The study concluded that post-secondary schools in south-south are ineffective due to inadequate financing and poor funds management among the school heads

5.1. Summary of Findings

The study explored the significant influence of strategy formulation, strategy implementation, and strategy evaluation and control on the performance of tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria. Key findings include: effective strategy formulation significantly influences the long-term success and performance of tertiary institutions. Institutions with well-developed strategies that align with their vision, mission, and external environment tend to perform better. It was found that successful implementation of strategies is crucial to achieving institutional goals. However, challenges such as resource constraints, inadequate training, and resistance to change often hinder the effective implementation of formulated strategies. The study highlighted the importance of continuous evaluation and control mechanisms to monitor progress and make adjustments. Institutions that regularly evaluate their strategies are better positioned to adapt to changes and sustain high performance.

5.2. Conclusion

The research concludes that the integration of communication, resource allocation, leadership and commitment play a pivotal role in determining the overall performance of tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria. Institutions that adopt a holistic approach to strategy implementation are more likely to achieve improved educational outcomes, enhanced institutional reputation, and increased operational efficiency. It was concluded that communication, resource allocation, leadership and commitment have significant and positive influence on performance of selected tertiary institutions in South-South Nigeria.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings, it was recommended that:

i Tertiary institutions should prioritize the establishment of clear, open, and transparent communication channels between leadership, staff, and student that align with institution's strategic goals and performance expectations and also fostering a positive organizational culture that improving overall performance.

ii Institution should allocate resources in alignment with the strategic goals of the institution that will enable them to achieve their full potential.

iii Institutions should invest in leadership development programs for both academic and administrative leaders. These programs should focus on skills such as strategic thinking, communication, and team management by fostering a culture of commitment among staff and improved performance across the institution.

References

- Abdalla, G. (2015). The relationship between strategic planning and firm performance. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 2(6): 201-213.
- Adedayo, S. A., and Olalekan, O. S. (2022). Resource allocation and strategy implementation in Nigerian universities: Implications for higher education performance. *African Journal of Educational Management*, 7(1), 45-59.
- Adeleke, A, Ogundele, O. J. K and Oyenuga, O. O. (2018). *Business policy and strategy*, (2nd ed.). Lagos: Concept Publications, 116p
- Agwu, M.E. (2018). Analysis of the impact of strategic management on the business performance of SMEs in Nigeria. *Academy of Strategic Management Journal*, 17(1):1-20.
- Akarika, D. C., Umoren, P. E., and Ikon, A. O. (2023). Employee communication practice and communication climate of tertiary institutions in Nigeria. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Management Review*, 4(5). Retrieved from
- Akanbi, M. O., and Fadare, M. O. (2020). Strategic management and university performance: A review of literature. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 11(24), 22-29.

- Akingbade, D. W. and Fasogbon, Z. A. (2015). Does long range planning improve company performance? *Management Review*, September, 2(7):19-31.
- Alaka, M.; Tijani, H. and Abass, T. (2011). Impact of strategic planning on small and medium-sized enterprises. *Journal of Economics*, 5(1): 45-55.
- Ali, A. and Al-jaradi, I. (2016). *Essentials of Modern Management (Principles and Elements)* (2nd Edition). Lagos: "B" Concept Press. 181p.
- Ali, S., and Rehman, Z. (2021). Impact of Organizational Commitment on Employee Performance: A Mediated Model of Resource Allocation and Leadership Styles. *International Journal of Management*, 32(2), 154-168.
- Alharbi, A., and Ameen, A. (2022). The Role of Leadership and Resource Allocation in Enhancing Organizational Performance: Evidence from the Public Sector in Saudi Arabia. *Public Administration Review*, 82(1), 85-98.
- Al-Nashash, H. (2020). Leadership in strategy implementation in higher education institutions: The case of the Middle East. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 34(6), 1267-1285.
- Amin, M., and Shaukat, Z. (2019). Resource Allocation and Organizational Performance: Evidence from Manufacturing Firms. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 10(7), 58-66.
- Anichebe, I. and Agu, S. (2015). Strategy formulation and implementations in organizations. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 6(12): 30-37.
- Aremu, E. (2016). An empirical investigation of aspects of strategy formulation and implementation within large private manufacturing firms in Kenya. unpublished Doctoral Thesis, Strathclyde University, 186p.
- Aremu, E. and Olodo, H. (2015). Strategic management and performance of SMEs. *Journal of Economics and Management*, 4(3):33-45.
- Ayanda, T. and Oyinloye, D. (2014). Effects of strategic planning in the Nigerian Financial Sector: Empirical insight from selected banks in Lagos State. *Journal of Social Development*, 5(1):96-108.
- Ayandele, I. A. (2019). *Business Policy and Strategic Management*, Douala: Tropical Focus International, 315p.
- Ayandele, I. A. (2019). *Business Policy and Strategic Management*, Douala: Tropical Focus International, 315p.
- Barney, J. B. (1991). Firm resources and sustained competitive advantage. *Journal of Management*, 17(1), 99-120.

- Brown, T., and Jones, M. (2020). Strategic alignment of tertiary education institutions with industry needs. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 42(5), 472-489.
- Brownson, C. D., Umanah, A. E., and Uwa, K. L. (2024). Strategic management practices and organisational performance in Akwa Ibom State civil service. *British Journal of Management and Marketing Studies*, 7(2).
- Chima T. (2023). Performance Management and Employees' Commitment in Tertiary Institutions in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Journal management and accounting*, 2(3), 39-78.
- Chukwu, M. O., and Ugochukwu, E. A. (2021). Organizational culture and institutional performance in Nigerian tertiary institutions: The role of leadership and innovation. *Journal of Business Research*, 14(3), 56-70.
- Daniel Akarika (2023). examined an appraisal of organizational communication and job Satisfaction among academic staff in Akwa Ibom State University. *Journal management and accounting*, 2(3), 15-29.
- Edwards, B. (2013). Strategy formulation and profitability. *European Scientific Journal*, 11(16):57-69.
- Efi, A.; Udofia, N. and Imagha, O.(2018). Impact of Strategic Planning on Organizational Performance of University of Uyo. *International Journal of Management Studies, Business & Entrepreneurship Research*, 3(3):94-110.
- Effiong, M. E., and Bassey, A. E. (2021). Influence of leadership and commitment on performance in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State. *Journal of Management and Administration Studies*, 10(3), 55-68.
- Ekanem, E. A., Udo, G. S., and Ita, V. E. (2019). Communication and organizational performance in Nigerian tertiary institutions: A case study of Akwa Ibom State. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 7(5), 47-61.
- Eze, M. O., and Nwosu, C. N. (2020). Strategic management practices in Nigerian universities: Challenges and prospects. *African Journal of Education and Social Sciences*, 9(1), 72-80.
- Fainstein, J., and Defihippis, A.N., (2015). Strategic planning, performance and innovative capabilities of non-family members in family businesses. *International Journal of Innovation Management*, 2(7):11-23.
- Fides, D., Chukwumah, F. and Ezeugbor, E. (2015). Problems of implementation of strategic plans for secondary schools' improvement in Anambra State. *Journal of Management Development*, 6(8): 26-33.
- Flapper, S. D. P., Fortuin, L., and Stoop, P. P. (2016). Towards consistent performance management systems. *International Journal of Operations and Production Management*, 16(7): 27-37.

- Gluck, R. (2014). *Essential readings in Business Strategy*. London: Palgrave, 146p.
- González, J., and Martínez, M. (2021). Evaluating strategic plans in higher education: The role of performance measurement. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 49(3), 463-485.
- Harrison, A. and Porter, J. (2015). The strategic implementation process; evoking strategic consensus through communication. *Journal of Business Research*, 55(4):301-310.
- Harrison, J., and Carroll, B. (2020). Strategic planning in higher education institutions: A review of global best practices. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 58(4), 312-326.
- Hassan, E. (2015). Strategy formulation and profitability in manufacturing Firms. *Administrative Sciences*, 7(4): 1-19.
- Hieu, V. and Nwachukwu, C. (2019). Strategy evaluation process and strategic performance nexus. *Management Review*, 4(3):43-54.
- Hitt, S. (2016). Evaluating Strategies. *European Scientific Journal*, 9(2):21-32.
- Hossain, M., and Ghosh, P. (2021). Adapting strategies to external changes: Evidence from tertiary institutions during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Higher Education Quarterly*, 75(1), 112-127.
- Hunger, J.D. and Wheelen, T.L. (2015). *Concepts in Strategic Management and Business Policy*. UK: Pearson Education, 269P.
- Ike, S. and Uzochukwu, M. (2021). The impact of resource-based view on the strategic management of Nigerian universities. *African Journal of Educational Management*, 29(3), 45-58.
- Ikon, E. and Nwankwo, D. (2016). Strategy development and profitability of manufacturing companies in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 7(3): 41-49.
- Itighise, A. E., and Akpaetor, F. B. (2014). Digital media and information dissemination in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Journal of Information Engineering and Applications*, 4(11). Retrieved from
- Izuka, C., and Ukpai, U. E. (2024). Performance management and employee commitment in tertiary institutions in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Global Journal of Applied, Management and Social Sciences*. Retrieved from
- Joanna, S. (2014). Obstacles to implementation of strategy and the sales in Polish companies. *Journal of Management and Strategy*, 3(1): 22-31.
- Lee, S., and Park, J. (2022). The role of performance evaluation systems in enhancing the effectiveness of higher education institutions. *Studies in Higher Education*, 47(2), 178-190.

- Magaisa, J. and Matipira, E. (2017). Strategy evaluation and control and performance of SMEs in Zimbabwe. *Journal of Management*, 4(2):19-36.
- Manzoor, F. (2023). Resource Allocation and Employee Performance: A Moderated Mediation Model of Commitment and Leadership. *Journal of Healthcare Management*, 48(4), 296-310.
- Maroa, J. G. and Muturi, W. (2015). Influence of Strategic Management Practices on Performance of Floriculture Firms in Kenya. A Study of Kiambu County Kenya. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce & Management*. 3(7): 497-513.
- McQuity, C. (2017). Strategic management in an enacted world. *Academy of Management Review*, 10(5):724-736.
- Meier, K.; O'Toole, L; Boyne, G. and Walker, R. (2017). Strategic management and the performance of public organizations: Testing venerable ideas against recent theories. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 17(3): 19-29.
- Musyoka, N. (2017). Identifying and appraising how managers install strategy. *Strategic Management Journal*, 8(3): 1-14.
- Nkansah, K., and Yeboah, F. (2021). Barriers to strategy implementation in tertiary institutions: A case study from Ghana. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 35(7), 1217-1232.
- Nwajiuba, C. U., and Adetunji, M. A. (2020). Employability of graduates in Nigerian universities: The South-South perspective. *Journal of Higher Education in Africa*, 18(1), 102-116.
- Nwosu, P. O., Ibi, M. B., Salihu, D. J., and Chidinma, N. P. (2024). Educational financing, fund management, and the effectiveness of post-secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Journal of Association of Educational Management and Policy Practitioners*, 2(1), 17-29. Retrieved from
- O'Boyle, E. H., Forsyth, D. R., & Banks, G. C. (2021). Strategy implementation: A review and an introductory framework. *European Management Journal*, 39(1), 22-33.
- Oduro, D., and Agyekum, K. (2022). Strategic planning and the performance of universities in sub-Saharan Africa. *Africa Education Review*, 19(1), 1-20.
- Ogunyemi, A. O., and Adebayo, S. O. (2021). Leadership commitment and strategy implementation in Nigerian universities: The role of top management. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Administration*, 14(1), 23-36.
- Okafor, C. and Ifeanyi, A. (2020). Strategic resource management and institutional performance: Insights from Nigerian universities. *Journal of Educational Policy and Practice*, 22(4), 112-130.
- Okafor, F. E. (2019). Strategic planning in Nigerian higher education institutions: Challenges and opportunities. *Journal of Educational Research and Practice*, 9(2), 15-24.

- Okoli, I. E., Nnabuife, E. K., Adani, N. I., and Ugbo, I. E. (2021). Transformational leadership and organizational success: Evidence from tertiary institutions. *Quarterly Reviews*, 4(1), 170–182. Retrieved from
- Okolie, U. L., and Egbe, S. O. (2020). Communication and organizational performance in Nigerian higher education institutions: A case study of universities in the South-South region. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 9(2), 110-121.
- Olayiwola, A. O., and Oladipo, S. A. (2021). Higher education performance and regional development in Nigeria: Insights from the South-South zone. *African Journal of Education and Development Studies*, 5(2), 67-80.
- Okon, E. E., Akpanim, N. E., & Usoro, M. (2022). Manpower planning and organizational effectiveness in Akwa Ibom State University. *Global Journal of Human Resource Management*, 10(3), 1-50. Retrieved from
- Okorafor, C. O., and Opara, G. N. (2020). Resource allocation and performance outcomes in Nigerian universities. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 42(4), 365-379. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1360080X.2020.1797681>
- Omotayo, F. O., and Olayinka, F. O. (2021). Strategic Management and Organizational Performance in Nigerian Tertiary Institutions. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 35(4), 243-260.
- Obi, N. A. (2021). Strategic management and its role in the development of Nigerian universities: A case study of the South-South zone. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 43(1), 46-58.
- Saidu, M. A., and Adebayo, O. A. (2022). Strategic evaluation in Nigerian universities: Barriers to effective assessment. *Journal of Strategic Management in Education*, 14(3), 104-115.
- Udo, G. S., Effiong, E. O., and Bassey, P. E. (2018). Leadership styles and their impact on institutional performance in Nigeria's tertiary education sector. *Journal of Educational Leadership and Policy Studies*, 7(1), 15-29.
- Vigfússon, K., Jóhannsdóttir, L., & Ólafsson, S. (2021). Obstacles to strategy implementation and success factors: a review of empirical literature. *Strategic Management*, 26(2), 1-14. Retrieved from
- Wang, Z., and Xu, Y. (2020). Transformational Leadership and Organizational Performance: Mediating Role of Employee Commitment. *Journal of Business Research*, 124, 383-392.
- Zohreh, K., and Soltani, M. (2023). Aligning academic and administrative functions with institutional strategy: A comparative analysis. *Journal of University Management*, 50(4), 555-570.